

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This documentation contains instructions for setting up the JSBACH model forced by the output from storm-resolving models to quantify the carbon fluxes and stocks over Europe.

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WP8

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1 Executive summary

This report presents the deliverable associated with WP8.6, which is about documenting the setup of offline terrestrial biosphere simulations driven by the output of the NextGEMS 5-km ICON model to estimate carbon fluxes and storage. It describes the required land forcing data for vegetation and soil parameters, initial states, and atmospheric forcing data, along with the procedures used to generate the forcing data and to spin up the biosphere model. In particular, the carbon pools need to be spun up, so that the carbon reaches equilibrium with the atmosphere, which can take hundreds to thousands of years, especially for humus pools. To minimize computing time, a separate workflow is used to estimate the equilibrium carbon conditions of humus pools and a downscaling spin-up strategy is developed. The workflow adjusts humus pools based on the analytical prediction of the equilibrium concentration of carbon in humus pools, extrapolating from their transient behaviour. This workflow saves 63.48% of the otherwise required time for spin-up. The downscaling spin-up strategy consists of spinning up the carbon pools first using a grid spacing of 160 km and then of 5 km. But the downscaling spin-up strategy turns out to not reduce the required spin-up time. Hence, we only use the adjusting humus pools workflow and show that we can indeed spin up the carbon pools for a domain the size of Europe, with a grid spacing of 5 km. 473 years are required to complete the spin-up, equivalent to about 3 days of computation using eight nodes of the supercomputer Levante. Finally, a step-by-step tutorial explaining the setup of the offline terrestrial biosphere simulations is provided, with accompanying workflows available at 'https://gitlab.dkrz.de/m300793/scripts_offline_jsbach.git'.

2 Conclusion & Results

This report serves as the deliverable for WP8.6 "Documentation for setting up offline terrestrial biosphere simulations", focusing on setting up the offline JSBACH model and spinning up JSBACH using the output from the NextGEMS global storm-resolving ICON model.

First, we provide an overview of the required land forcing data, atmospheric forcing data, and the process for obtaining these data. Second, we test various spin-up strategies aimed at reducing the time required to spin up the land carbon pools, revealing that i) the workflow to adjust humus pools based on the analytical prediction of the equilibrium concentration of carbon of the humus pools saves 63.48% of the spin-up time, and ii) including a downscaling step by first spinning up a coarser-resolution simulation does not save spin-up time.

Based upon these findings, we set up our final computational domain for offline JSBACH carbon flux simulations as covering Europe (279,900 points), encompassing 28 countries of the European Union and Eastern Europe where dense forests exist. The final grid spacing is 5 km, in agreement with the resolution of ICON. From past studies, carbon pools are considered as spun up when the absolute difference in total ecosystem carbon is less than $1 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ at each grid cell. We show that the carbon pools of our simulation are indeed spun up after 473 years (Fig. 8). This required 2.96 days of computation using eight nodes of the supercomputer Levante at DKRZ. The model is ready to be used for the science planned in WP9.4, estimating carbon stocks and fluxes over Europe with the JSBACH model using the output from the

NextGEMS global storm-resolving ICON model.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	yes
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	yes

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP8	Relevance in this deliverable?
Evaluate surface energy, water and momentum balance components as well as near-surface meteorology over land at storm-resolving resolution against observations and coarser resolution simulations (O1)	no

Objectives of WP8	Relevance in this deliverable?
Represent land-surface heterogeneities at storm-resolving resolution by making use of the latest generation remote sensing products of land cover and vegetation (O1)	no
Prepare the NextGEMS models to best serve the science and applications, by implementing online output statistics co-developed with stakeholders, with a pilot project focusing on solar energy (O1 and O3)	no
Expand scope of the SR-ESM by coupling it offline to a terrestrial biosphere model (O1)	yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Introduction

The storm-resolving models developed in NextGEMS are able to capture landscape details, small-scale atmospheric processes, and their interactions with the land surface, such as between soil moisture and convective precipitation. This significantly influences the spatial distribution of precipitation and the probability distribution function of precipitation rates (precipitation frequency) compared to conventional coarse-resolution climate models. This, in turn, is expected to affect vegetation dynamics and, together with the better resolution of surface fields, carbon fluxes, and storage. The goal of WP8.6 was to set up an offline version of a terrestrial biosphere model (JSBACH) driven by the output of the 5-km ICON model. This set-up will then be used in WP9.4 to estimate carbon fluxes and carbon storage over Europe.

As written in the description of WP8.6 in the NextGEMS proposal, an offline version of the terrestrial biosphere model JSBACH has to be set up over a simulation domain covering Europe, using storm-resolving resolution, and driven by the output of the ICON storm-resolving simulation. This approach will then be used in task 9.4 to estimate carbon stocks and fluxes over Europe. This task only tests the technicalities by using the short preparatory runs from the development cycles as driver. It has to ensure that all the necessary inputs to JSBACH are present in the storm-resolving run. It also has to set up the grid, the land surface data for JSBACH, and develop strategies to initialize the carbon pool that takes many years to spin up.

In agreement with this planned work, in this report, we report in sections 4.2 and 4.3 about the required land and atmospheric forcing data, while section 4.4 elaborates on spin-up strategies. Section 4.5 presents the final domain setup and demonstrates that we can spin up the carbon pools using a domain covering Europe and a grid spacing of 5 km, fulfilling the planned work of WP8.6. Finally, section 4.6 provides a step-by-step tutorial to set up and run the offline JSBACH model version driven by ICON output at storm-resolving scales.

4.2 Land forcing data

To simulate carbon, JSBACH first needs to know the characteristics of the land surface, meaning the surface, vegetation and soil characteristics. This information must be provided for the simulation domain and with the appropriate resolution, in our case chosen to be 5 km. The required data are listed in Tables 1 to 5. We list the variable names requested by JSBACH, what the variables represent and in which files the variables are stored. The variables in Tables 1 to 4 are prescribed and not directly evolved by JSBACH. In contrast, the variables in Table 5 are prognostic variables that will change throughout the simulation time, but they require an initial value and need to be spun up. We describe in the next paragraph the procedure employed to generate the data listed in Tables 1 to 5.

Table 1: Fraction of various entities. Note that JSBACH uses 11 plant functional types.

Variable name	Description	File name
sea	fraction of ocean with respect to a grid box	bc_land_frac_11pfts.nc
fract_land	fraction of land with respect to a grid box	”
fract_veg	fraction of vegetated tile with respect to land tile	”
veg_ratio_max	maximum fraction that can be covered by vegetation with respect to vegetated tile	”
fract_lake	fraction of lake with respect to a grid box	”
fract_glac	fraction of glacier with respect to land tile	”
fract_pft01 ~ fract_pft11	fraction of each plant functional type with respect to veg_ratio_max	”

Table 2: Orography information.

Variable name	Description	File name
elevation	geometric height of the earth’s surface above sea level	bc_land_sso.nc
orostd	standard deviation of subgrid scale orography	”

Table 3: Soil properties.

Variable name	Description	File name
soil_depth	soil depth until bedrock	bc_land_soil.nc
root_depth	depth of root zone	"
fract_org_sl	fraction of soil organic carbon within soil layer	"
bclapp	Clapp and Hornberger parameter b	"
soil_field_cap	volumetric soil field capacity	"
heat_capacity	heat capacity of dry soil	"
heat_conductivity	heat conductivity of dry soil	"
hyd_cond_sat	saturated hydraulic conductivity	"
moisture_pot	saturated matrix potential	"
pore_size_index	soil pore size distribution index	"
soil_porosity	volumetric soil porosity	"
wilting_point	volumetric wilting point	"
fao	soil type based on FAO dataset	"
maxmoist	maximum soil water capacity used for hydrology	"

Table 4: Further surface characteristics.

Variable name	Description	File name
roughness_length	surface roughness length	bc_land_phys.nc
roughness_length_oro	roughness length due to orography	"
albedo_soil_vis	soil albedo in the visible range	"
albedo_soil_nir	soil albedo in the near-infrared range	"

Table 5: Prognostic variables. Note that the initial state of soil temperature in each soil layer is not directly provided. Rather, in the JSBACH model, it is generated from the initial land surface temperature as a sinusoidal function of soil layer depth and days in a year. This is because it is difficult to get information on deeper soil temperature.

Variable name	Description	File name
layer_moist	Initial soil moisture for each soil layer	ic_land_soil.nc
surf_temp	Initial land surface temperature	"
snow	Initial snow depth	"
lai_clim	Initial leaf area index	bc_land_phys.nc
c_green	Carbon pool for leaves, fine roots, vegetative organs and other green parts of vegetation	starting from 0
c_woods	Carbon pool for stems, thick roots and other (dead) structural material of living vegetation	"
c_reserve	Carbon pool for carbohydrate reserve (sugars, starches) that allows plants to survive bad times	"
c_crop_harvest	Carbon pool for biomass harvested from crops	"
c_bg_sum	Sum of below-ground carbon pools	"
c_ag_sum_1	Sum of above-ground carbon pools (e.g., litter)	"
c_sum_humus	Sum of humus carbon pools	"
c_sum_natural	total ecosystem carbon	"

In our NextGEMS 5-km global ICON simulation, the atmosphere and the land interact with each other, and the land is also represented by the JSBACH model, but only the physical land processes are retained. This means that we do not simulate carbon and we use neither interactive leaves nor dynamical vegetation. In contrast, for our offline JSBACH simulation, we want to simulate carbon fluxes and storage. To do so, we need to use plant functional types and we need at least the leaves to be interactive. We do not simulate a fully dynamical vegetation as this would only be important for simulations over thousands of years when different vegetation species can colonize new habitats. In practical terms, from all the variables listed in Tables 1 to 5, only the variables `fract_pft01...fract_pft11` were not already employed by ICON and thus already available on a 5-km global grid. For the already available variables, we just crop their global domain to the area of interest, see Fig. 1 for the chosen final integration domain (refer to section 4.6 for technical details). The fractions of plant functional types (PFTs) need additional procedures. First, fractions are extracted from the ESA-CCI land cover data set, that provides observed PFTs at 300 m resolution (Store, 2019) (see Fig. 2a). Second, these PFTs are converted to the PFTs employed by JSBACH using a cross-walking table and the resulting fractions

are interpolated onto the model grid and cropped to the area of interest. Third, given the high resolution of the targeted simulation, fractions of PFTs in each grid box are converted into one dominant PFT per grid box (see Fig. 2b) (refer to section 4.6.4 for detailed technical procedures).

Figure 1: Chosen final model domain at a grid spacing of 5 km, together with topography.

(a) ESA CCI PFTs at 300 m

(b) Dominant PFT based interpolated ESA CCI PFTs at 5 km

Figure 2: (a) The number of ESA-CCI PFTs at 300 m resolution and (b) converted dominant one PFT per grid box. PFTs in JSBACH are categorized into 11 PTFs: 1) Tropical broadleaf evergreen, 2) Tropical broadleaf deciduous, 3) Extra-tropical evergreen, 4) Extra-tropical deciduous, 5) Raingreen shrubs, 6) Deciduous shrubs, 7) C3 grass, 8) C4 grass, 9) C3 pasture, 10) C4 pasture, and 11) C3 crops.

As said earlier, the variables listed in Table 5 evolve over time with hourly timestep, starting from the initial states provided in the corresponding files. They need to be spun up. As their spin-up time is much shorter than the slowly varying carbon pools, we describe in section 4.4 how we spin up carbon. By the time carbon is spun up, all the land physical parameters will also be spun up. All carbon pool variables in Table 5 are not initialized by land forcing data and start from zero amount. Thus, we need to spin up those carbon fields. The description of the spin-up will be given in Section 4.4.

4.3 Atmospheric forcing data

To simulate carbon, JSBACH also needs atmospheric forcing data that should be provided at the interface between the land and the atmosphere as boundary conditions. The needed data are surface precipitation, air humidity close to the surface, temperature close to the surface, shortwave and longwave radiation at the surface, as well as wind speed close to the surface. These variables evolve with time and are provided to JSBACH every 3 h. They are derived from the output of our global 5-km NextGEMS ICON simulation. A workflow extracts the needed variables from the HEALPix output of ICON. Then, similar to what was done for the land forcing data in section 4.2, the workflow crops the variables to the area of interest (refer to section 4.6 for detailed technical procedures). The workflow is called 'ngc4jsb.bash', and is accessible at 'https://gitlab.dkrz.de/m300793/scripts_offline_jsbach.git'.

4.4 Spin-up

The JSBACH model initializes carbon fluxes and storage at zero amount, as indicated in section 4.2. As such, these fields are not in equilibrium with the atmospheric forcing at the initial time and the model needs to be spun up until the fields reach their equilibrium values, as commonly done in the modelling community (Yang et al., 1995; Dickinson et al., 1998). Given that these fields are controlled by very slow processes, spin-up for terrestrial biosphere simulations typically takes centuries or millennia (Shi et al., 2013).

In particular, strongly recalcitrant organic matter (humus) pools take the longest spin-up time. To speed up the time needed to reach an equilibrium state, the JSBACH model provides a workflow 'equilibrate_humus.ksh'. The workflow analytically predicts the equilibrium value of the humus pools from their transient behaviour and replaces the current value of the humus pools with this analytically predicted value. Then the spin-up is continued until equilibrium is indeed reached. It is recommended to apply the workflow when the long-term average carbon flux into humus pools reaches a steady state so that the workflow can predict equilibrium. In this report, we apply the workflow at the time when the difference in carbon flux into the humus pool between two consecutive years is smaller than 0.001 g C m^{-2} at all grid points (see Fig. 3), a more strict threshold than the one used to check final equilibrium (see next paragraph).

To quantify the benefit of the workflow, we conducted two spin-up simulations using a smaller domain and coarser grid spacing to reduce computing time. This smaller test domain covers Germany at a grid spacing of 160 km (Fig. 5a). As in previous coarse-resolution offline carbon simulations (McGuire et al., 1992; Hoffman et al., 2014), the condition for equilibrium is that the absolute difference in total ecosystem carbon between years is less than 1 g C m^{-2} at each grid cell. The first simulation is called NOT_ADJUSTED. It has been spun up for 800 years without using the workflow to accelerate the equilibration of the humus pool. NOT_ADJUSTED has not reached the equilibrium state even after 800 years (see Fig. 4a). In contrast, the second simulation is called ADJUSTED and it is spun up using the humus pool workflow (Fig. 3). Its carbon fluxes into humus pools are in steady state after around 340 years and thus the workflow is applied at that time (Fig. 3). Further running the simulation for another 60 years (Fig. 4b) indeed confirms that the total ecosystem carbon has equilibrated. In part through extrapolation, Fig. 4 shows how many years the two simulations need to reach the equilibrium state of total ecosystem carbon. ADJUSTED reaches the equilibrium after 369 years, whereas NOT_ADJUSTED arrives would need more or less 1300 spin-up years. As a result, with 'equilibrate_humus.ksh' we can save 931 spin-up years, equivalent to 6.48 CPU hours even for such a small simulation domain and coarse grid spacing.

Figure 3: Time series of (a) annual carbon flux into humus pools and (b) the percentage of grid points not yet in steady state according to the time evolution of the carbon flux into humus pool. Output from the ADJUSTED simulation.

Figure 4: Time series of (a) carbon in humus pool and (b) total ecosystem carbon. Both panels (a) and (b) show ADJUSTED (blue solid) and NOT_ADJUSTED (orange solid) and panel (b) shows the value of the equilibrium state (blue dash) and logarithmic curve fit to NOT_ADJUSTED (orange dash).

Even if the workflow drastically reduces the amount of spin-up years that have to be simulated, simulating 400 years may take quite some time when using a much bigger domain with a much finer grid spacing. Hence, we tested a downscaling spin-up strategy with the aim of achieving equilibrium states of carbon fields even faster. Conventional spin-up starts from zero carbon concentrations at the targeted resolution (Hoffman et al., 2014; Shi et al., 2013). In contrast, our downscaling strategy first spins up the carbon fields at a coarser resolution, and then uses that equilibrium state to initialize the carbon fields of the higher-resolution simulation. This strategy is expected to enable shorter spin-up times for the highest resolution, as the initial carbon fields start from values closer to their equilibrium states.

Figure 5: Overview of the simulation domain and grid spacings used to evaluate the downscaling spin-up strategy. Shown is topography (m) for grid spacings of (a) 160 km and (b) 5 km.

To find the best spin-up strategy, we thus compare two types of spin-up approaches. The first one spins up the 5-km stimulation starting from carbon concentrations set to zero, and is called `CONVENTIONAL_5km`. The second one spins up first the model at 160 km, which is equivalent to the `ADJUSTED` simulation above (now it is called `CONVENTIONAL_160km`), and then uses this equilibrium state to spin up the simulation at 5 km (`DOWNSCALING_160km->5km`).

These tests were conducted on a smaller domain covering parts of Germany to minimize computational time, allowing easier testing of the spin-up strategies (Fig. 5). Table 6 summarizes the requested total spin-up times for the simulations, whereas Fig. 6a shows the evolution of total ecosystem carbon and Fig. 6b the evolution of the percentage of non-equilibrated grid cells. In `CONVENTIONAL_5km`, equilibrium is reached after 348 years of simulation, corresponding to 16.43 hours of real-time computation on one node of the supercomputer Levante at DKRZ (i.e., 16.43 CPU hours). The sudden changes of total ecosystem carbon in Fig. 6 between year 330 and 350 indicate when humus pools are adjusted. In comparison, `DOWNSCALING_160->5km` reaches its equilibrium after 336 years of simulation, corresponding to 15.87 hours. Even if the downscaling spin-up strategy slightly reduces the time by 0.56 hours, the total computing time consumed by `CONVENTIONAL_160km` and `DOWNSCALING_160km->5km` is 18.43 CPU hours. Hence, the inclusion of a downscaling step does not help to save CPU hours.

Table 6: Summary of spin-up timing statistics for the tested spin-up strategies using one node of the supercomputer Levante at DKRZ. The abbreviation SYPM denotes simulated year per minute.

Simulation name	Grid cells (#)	Simulation years	SYPM	CPU hours
CONVENTIONAL_160km	29	368 years	2.4 years	2.56
CONVENTIONAL_5km	3,040	348 years	0.35 years	16.43
DOWNSCALING_160km->5km	3,040	336 years	0.35 years	15.87

Figure 6: (a) Time series of changes in total ecosystem carbon (ΔC_{tot}) averaged over the simulation domain. Inset shows zoom in the region between $-5 < \Delta C_{tot} < 5$ except for DOWNSCALING_160km->5km, to better reveal the variations in C_{tot} . (b) Time series of the fraction of grid points not yet equilibrated. Both panels (a) and (b) show CONVENTIONAL_160km (orange), CONVENTIONAL_5km (blue), and DOWNSCALING_160km->5km (red). Dots indicate when equilibrium is achieved.

4.5 Final set-up

As given in the description of WP8.6, our final simulation domain should cover Europe. The chosen domain is shown in Fig. 1. It covers 28 countries of the European Union and Eastern Europe where dense forests exist. We prepared all the required land and atmospheric forcing data according to Sections 4.2 and 4.3 and spun up the simulation according to Section 4.4. Reaching equilibrium values of total ecosystem carbon takes 473 simulation years for a grid spacing of 5 km. This requires about 2.96 real days of computation with eight nodes, corresponding to 567.6 CPU hours. Eight nodes give the best efficiency (Fig. 7). Figure 8 demonstrates that the carbon field is fully spun up after humus pools are adjusted at year 413 when total ecosystem carbon suddenly changes.

Table 7: Summary of spin-up timing statistics over the final European domain.

Simulation name	Grid cells (#)	Simulation years	SYPM	CPU hours
CONVENTIONAL_5km	279,900	473 years	0.11 years	567.6

Figure 7: Averaged time needed for one-year simulation over the final European domain with the different number of nodes.

Figure 8: Same as Fig. 6, but over the final European domain for CONVENTIONAL_5km.

4.6 Tutorial: how to set up offline terrestrial biosphere simulation

This section demonstrates the step-by-step procedure for setting up the offline terrestrial biosphere simulation using JSBACH for the final domain. The examples are procedures to generate land and atmospheric forcing data, set up the final domain, and spin up the simulation. Note that this tutorial is based on the environment of the supercomputer Levante at DKRZ. In ICON jargon, a grid spacing of 5 km is referred to as R2B9.

4.6.1 Necessary software, library and basic setup

Necessary software and library:

- Git (<https://git-scm.com/>)
- FORTRAN (<https://fortran-lang.org/>)
- CDO (<https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo>)
- Slurm (<https://slurm.schedmd.com/quickstart.html>) or equivalent job scheduling tool (in this case, job scheduling lines in the tutorial need to be replaced with the selected job scheduling tool).
- Python and Jupyter Notebook (<https://www.python.org/>)

Declare environmental variables and get scripts to handle forcing data:

```
base_dir=<your base directory path>
cd ${base_dir}
mkdir Carbon

git clone git@gitlab.dkrz.de:m300793/scripts_offline_jsbach.git ./script
script=${base_dir}/script
```

4.6.2 Prepare JSBACH source code

Get JSBACH source code:

```
git clone --recursive git@gitlab.dkrz.de:icon/icon-mpim.git ljsb-hr-std

cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/ljsb-hr-std
git checkout land-dev
git submodule update

cd externals/jsbach
git checkout feature/hydrotiles
```

Install JSBACH:

```
cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/1jsb-hr-std

./config/dkrz/levante.intel-2021.5.0 --enable-openmp

make -j32
```

4.6.3 Prepare grid file

Clone and install grid generator source code:

```
cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/

git clone --recursive \
git@gitlab.dkrz.de:mpim-sw/grid-generator.git \
grid-generator

cd grid-generator
./config/dkrz/levante.intel --enable-openmp
make -j32
mkdir grids
```

Create land mask file for the grid:

This step creates a land mask file that has the land grid points only, as the JSBACH model cannot handle ocean grid points.

```
cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/grid-generator/grids

# create regmask
cp ${script}/get_grid_and_remask_files.bash .
./get_grid_and_remask_files.bash

cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/grid-generator/run

./make_target_runscript in_script=grid.create_EU_Icosahedron_grids
vi grid.create_EU_Icosahedron_grids.run
```

Add following lines and replace <account> by your account:

```
#!/bin/ksh
#-----
# Junhong Lee   MPI-M,   2024-02
```

```

#
#-----
#-----
# paths of directories
ACCOUNT=<account>
WORKDIR=${basedir}/grids
#-----
. ${thisdir}/create_grids_tools
#-----
# exapmle of creating a grid from a given cell mask in a file
inGridFile=icon_grid_0015_R02B09_G.nc
inMaskFile=regmask_0015_R02B09_EU.nc
maskField=lnd_cells
flagValue=1
outGridFile=icon_grid_0015_R02B09_EU.nc

get_grid_from_filemask $inGridFile $inMaskFile $maskField $flagValue $outGridFile

#inGridFile=icon_grid_0021_R02B06_G.nc
#inMaskFile=regmask_0021_R02B06_EU.nc
#maskField=lnd_cells
#flagValue=1
#outGridFile=icon_grid_0021_R02B06_EU.nc
#
#get_grid_from_filemask $inGridFile $inMaskFile $maskField $flagValue #outGridFile
#
#inGridFile=icon_grid_0043_R02B04_G.nc
#inMaskFile=regmask_0043_R02B04_EU.nc
#maskField=lnd_cells
#flagValue=1
#outGridFile=icon_grid_0043_R02B04_EU.nc
#
#get_grid_from_filemask $inGridFile $inMaskFile $maskField $flagValue $outGridFile
#-----

exit

```

Submit the job:

```

sbatch grid.create_germany_Icosahedron_grids.run

```

4.6.4 Prepare land input data

```

mkdir -p ${base_dir}/Carbon/land/EU

```

```
cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/land/EU

cp ${script}/create_land_input_files_EU.bash .
# Modify paths in the script

./create_land_input_files_EU.bash

# Execute copied Jupyter notebooks in sequence
cp ${script}/convert_ESA_CCI_to_11PFTs.ipynb .
cp ${script}/coarsen_and_remap_ESA_CCI_11PFTs.ipynb .
cp ${script}/convert_ESA_CCI_11PFTs_to_dominantPFT.ipynb .
```

4.6.5 Prepare atmospheric forcing data

Execute following lines after replacing <account> by your account:

```
mkdir ${base_dir}/Carbon/forcing
cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/forcing

cp ${script}/ngc4jsb.bash .

mkdir -p ${base_dir}/Carbon/forcing/global
cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/forcing/global

cp ${script}/ngc4jsb.bash .
ln -sf ${base_dir}/Carbon/grid-generator/grids/icon_grid_0015_R02B09_EU.nc .

# R2B9 global forcing (5 km)
salloc --x11 -p interactive -A <account> --mem=450GB \
ngc4jsb.bash -g icon_grid_0015_R02B09_EU.nc -s PT3H -y 2021 -d ngc3028

# If you encounter memory issues, please use sbatch as below or
# create forcing files every month, separately.
sbatch ngc4jsb_without_weights_daily.bash\
-g ${base_dir}/Carbon/grid-generator/grids/icon_grid_0015_R02B09_EU.nc \
-s PT3H -y 2024 -d ngc3028
```

4.6.6 Run offline JSBACH simulation

Initial run:

```
cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/1jsb-hr-std/run
```

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```
cp ${script}/t90_jsbalone_R2B9_EU.run .
# Modify paths and <account> in the script

sbatch t90_jsbalone_R2B9_EU.run

cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/1jsb-hr-std/experiments/e90_jsbalone_R2B9_EU
cp ${script}/clean-up-for-restart.bash .
# Modify paths in the script

./clean-up-for-restart.bash 2021
```

Spin-up run with your account for <account>:

```
cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/1jsb-hr-std/run
cp ${script}/t90_spin_up_auto.bash .
# Modify paths in the script

salloc --x11 -p shared -A <account> -t 360 t90_spin_up_auto.bash >& log.logt90_1 &
```

Adjust humus pools:

```
cd ${script}

# Execute the following jupyter notebook to know whether humus pools are
# ready to be adjusted
check_humus_t90.ipynb

# If it is ready in year YYYY-YYYY, execute the following procedures
cd ${base_dir}/Carbon/1jsb-hr-std/experiments/t90_jsbalone_R2B9_EU/`${YYYY-YYYY}`
cp ${script}/equilibrate_humus_jsbach4.ksh .
# Modify paths and parameters in the script

./equilibrate_humus_jsbach4.ksh
# Then, start spin-up run again
```

Check spin-up status:

```
cd ${script}

# Execute the following jupyter notebook
check_spin-up_t90.ipynb
```

5 References (Bibliography)

- Dickinson, R. E., M. Shaikh, R. Bryant, and L. Graumlich (1998). “Interactive canopies for a climate model”. In: *Journal of Climate* 11.11, pp. 2823–2836.
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- McGuire, A. D., J. M. Melillo, L. Joyce, D. W. Kicklighter, A. Grace, B. Moore III, and C. J. Vorosmarty (1992). “Interactions between carbon and nitrogen dynamics in estimating net primary productivity for potential vegetation in North America”. In: *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* 6.2, pp. 101–124.
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- Store, C. C. D. (2019). *Land cover classification gridded maps from 1992 to present derived from satellite observations*.
- Yang, Z.-L., R. Dickinson, A. Henderson-Sellers, and A. Pitman (1995). “Preliminary study of spin-up processes in land surface models with the first stage data of Project for Intercomparison of Land Surface Parameterization Schemes Phase 1 (a)”. In: *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 100.D8, pp. 16553–16578.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

This document will be freely available to the general public from the project website (<https://nextgems-h2020.eu>).

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

A one month delay due to colliding commitments during the hackathon preparations were communicated with the EC project officer.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The work presented in this deliverable contributes to the work in WP9, particularly task 9.4 (Carbon stocks over Europe) by preparing the offline terrestrial biosphere JSBACH simulation for carbon fluxes and storage over Europe.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden

- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2024
- "4th km-scale hackathon" (First nextGEMS application phase hackathon); 04. – 08. March 2024 in Hamburg

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>